

Newsletter 4 / 2020

To subscribe to/unsubscribe from this newsletter, please visit:

<https://lists.dkrz.de/mailman/listinfo/esiwace-external>

You find further details on ESIWACE at <https://www.esiwace.eu>.

All newsletters are also available at www.esiwace.eu/newsletter.

Deliverables and milestone documents referred to in the newsletters can be downloaded from Zenodo:

(<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>).

Contents

Save the date: ESIWACE2 Annual meeting and ENES HPC Workshop	1
Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in	1
News & updates	2
New seminar series on Machine Learning at ECMWF starting on 28 April	2
ESIWACE contributions to the EGU 2020 General Assembly (online only)	2
Second IS-ENES3 call for Access to Advanced Analysis Platforms for CMIP6 and CORDEX!	3
Snapshots	3
Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications	5

Save the date: ESIWACE2 Annual meeting and ENES HPC Workshop

The **ESIWACE2 Annual meeting 2020** will take place as a virtual event on Wednesday, May 27. It will be preceded and succeeded by the **6th ENES HPC Workshop on High Performance Computing for Climate and Weather**, which will be held as a virtual meeting on Monday and Tuesday May 25 & 26 and Thursday and Friday May 28 & 29.

Details at: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events>

Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [Special Interest Group IO in the UK](#), Reading, UK (online), 23 April, 2020
- [EGU 2020: Sharing Geoscience Online](#), online, 4-8 May, 2020
- [6th ENES HPC Workshop](#), online, 25-26 & 28-29 May, 2020

News & updates

New seminar series on Machine Learning at ECMWF starting on 28 April

ECMWF has launched a new seminar series featuring talks on machine learning for weather and climate predictions that is organised by Peter Dueben. All talks will be video-streamed. More details can be found [here](#). Please register to receive further information [here](#). The first seminar on the downscaling of precipitation predictions using Gaussian Processes will be live-streamed on 28th April 11:30 BST.

ESiWACE contributions to the EGU 2020 General Assembly (online only)

The EGU 2020 General Assembly has been turned into a virtual event this year (4-8 May 2020), for which everyone can [register](#) free of charge. Contributions of ESiWACE include assistance in the organisation of three sessions:

[State of the Art in Earth Science Data Visualization \(PICO\)](#)

Chat times Tuesday 5 May 2020 16:15-18:00 (CEST)

[Machine learning for Earth System modelling](#)

Chat times Wednesday 6 May 2020 14:00-15:45 and 16:15-18:00 (CEST)

[Progress in weather and climate modelling: improved data assimilation, better models, and higher resolution simulations](#)

- Chat times Thursday 7 May 2020 08:30-10:15 and 10:45-12:30 (CEST)

Second IS-ENES3 call for Access to Advanced Analysis Platforms for CMIP6 and CORDEX!

The IS-ENES3 project is broadening access to world-class supercomputers at the national facilities used by research communities in Germany, France, Italy and the UK. These facilities provide access to significant computational resources located next to **extensive data collections, including data from CMIP6 and CORDEX**. Thanks to funding from EU H2020, the IS-ENES3 project is able to provide **access free of charge to scientists from anywhere in Europe**. By applying for direct access to compute facilities, you will be able to discover the model data, process your multi-model analysis on the supercomputer and download the results. With the new **Access to Advanced Analysis Platforms**, you will be able to:

- 1) log onto a server that has direct access to the file system containing the data, allowing for the import of additional data on request
- 2) run your own software
- 3) have access to a large collection of software libraries commonly used to analyse climate model output.

The application deadline is **31.05.2020**. Calls are open twice a year, approximately every 6 months. More information on these new analysis platforms, the application procedure, and deadlines at:

<https://portal.enes.org/data/data-metadata-service/analysis-platforms>

Snapshots

BSC

EC-Earth4 has been deployed on Mare Nostrum 4. First runs and tests to produce valid initial conditions for computational analysis are under way. In parallel, BSC is running a battery of preliminary benchmarks resulting from integrating IFS and XIOS. The main objective will be to produce a realistic XIOS benchmark to assess the performance of the I/O server for next generation model runs.

Bull Atos

We are currently working in collaboration with the Cyprus Institute and NLeSC on the *medina* code generator to lower the memory consumption of the ECHAM GPU execution, thus increasing the number of processes running on GPU.

CERFACS

WP6: We are actively working on the SPOC (Small Private On-line Course) on OASIS3-MCT. The general structure of the course has been defined, the hands-on part of the course is finalised, and videos and specific exercises for each part are under development.

CMCC

The activity related to the design of the ESDM extensions for post-processing, analytics and visualization (PAV) has progressed, leading to the definition of a preliminary interface for PAV applications. CMCC contributed to the

Milestone 4.1 describing these activities. Some examples of these applications are being implemented using the proposed ESDM extensions. Furthermore, a benchmark of the Ophidia framework has been conducted to assess the current platform scalability limits using the resources awarded in the context of the project over the PRACE research infrastructure (at the BSC MareNostrum cluster).

DKRZ

We have finished archiving the DYAMOND Phase 1 output on tapes and are supporting MPI-M in the DYAMOND phase 2 experiments.

Due to COVID-19, the ENES HPC Workshop and the ESIWACE2 Annual meeting have been re-arranged to virtual meetings.

Niklas Röber has produced a video highlighting the fully coupled DYAMOND++ simulations that can be viewed in domes such as planetariums. It can be found at <https://nextcloud.dkrz.de/s/nDkmfFB9LxzfFr>, for watching on your laptop we recommend using the Amateras dome video player.

ECMWF

We have continued to improve the efficiency of our coupled model running at storm-resolving resolutions for the atmosphere. The work on the single precision NEMO model is progressing nicely and we have also continued to work hard on the porting of the spectral transformation to GPUs. Our latest paper on simulations with the Integrated Forecasting System with 1.45 km grid-spacing was accepted within the DYAMOND special issue of the *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan* and is now available as early online release:

https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/jmsj/advpub/0/advpub_2020-016/_article

ETH Zürich / CSCS

The Container Hackathon in Dec. 2019 was summarised in detail in Deliverable 2.8, which was submitted in Feb. 2020. CSCS, in conjunction with DKRZ, is now leveraging off of the hackathon experiences to complete the containerisation of the ICON model (with 'climate' physics) based on the latest ICON release candidate. This software has OpenACC directives and is thus GPU-capable, making it a significant challenge to run efficiently from within a container. To this end we use the SARUS container framework (<https://user.cscs.ch/tools/containers/sarus/>) developed at CSCS.

MPI-M

Calling CDO directly from the ESDM workflow management system has been discussed and decided. The streaming mechanism inside ESDM will handle the cross program streaming of data. We will extend CDO to use these streams. A simple variant of using ESDM inside CDO was already tested last year. Further tests are planned for 2020.

General CDO optimisation from the perspective of ensuring performance portability to heterogeneous architectures is progressing. Here, restructuring of CDO in terms of extendability, especially a first implementation of GPU-based operators, has made substantial progress. The first operators will be experimentally reworked in Q2 and Q3 of 2020.

FDB5 file structures are being developed and first experiments with the installed systems have been completed. Setup and control of the FDB5 systems is currently in the works, and in combination with the mentioned file structures a first implementation inside CDO will be enabled soon.

Met Office

We are making progress on halo exchange reduction in LFRic via more specific PSyclone function space declarations and redundant computation. The first was implemented in LFRic at the end of March, leading to about 16% of reduction in the number of halo swaps in routine runs with atmospheric physics. This approach has also paved the way for implementing redundant computation, scheduled for May, when LFRic will move to a new release of PSyclone and is expected to further reduce costs of communication.

Containerisation of LFRic is gaining popularity amongst the Met Office partners, who see it as a convenient approach for capturing the LFRic, quite complex, build dependencies as well as for testing the model. We are in the process of creating a Met Office GitHub repository as a central place for LFRic container recipes. This would also include updated Docker and Singularity container recipes from the ESIWACE2 Containerisation Hackathon in December 2019.

University of Reading

The ESIWACE [summer school](#) has accepted 30 attendees from all across the world in the first round and will subsidize them. Self-funded applicants can still apply for participation. The school will take place one way or another: We made the decision to reevaluate the situation with COVID-19 in May and to host it as a virtual event, if necessary.

With XIOS, we conducted the first test runs using ESDM as a NetCDF backend. We modified a shallow water model to use the native ESDM API, making further tests for robustness.

Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications

Dueben, P. D., Wedi, N., Saarinen, S. and Zeman, C.: Global Simulations of the Atmosphere at 1.45 km Grid-Spacing with the Integrated Forecasting System, Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II, [doi:10.2151/jmsj.2020-016](https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2020-016), 2020.

Neumann, P. and Biercamp, J.: ESIWACE: On European Infrastructure Efforts for Weather and Climate Modeling at Exascale, 2019 15th International Conference on eScience (eScience), San Diego, CA, USA, pp. 498-501, [doi:10.1109/eScience.2019.00065](https://doi.org/10.1109/eScience.2019.00065), 2019.

Saffin, L., Hatfield, S., Düben, P. and Palmer, T.: Reduced-precision parametrization: lessons from an intermediate-complexity atmospheric model, Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society, [doi:10.1002/qj.3754](https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3754), 2020.

The projects ESIWACE and ESIWACE2 have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 675191 and 823988